

Dynamic behaviors of aluminum foam based on the new empirical constitution

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ABSTRACT

A numerical model of the aluminium foam with voronoi cells is built and crushed with various velocities from 1m/s to 110m/s. It is shown that the foam deforms homogeneously within the whole specimen and the stress in the foam increases gradually with the strain without an obvious plateau stage under the low-velocity compression, while the deformation is concentrated within a zone near the impact end and an obvious plateau stage can be found in the stress-strain curves of the foams under the high-velocity crushing. The distribution of the density within the crushed foam is measured by the digital image processing. Accordingly, the distribution of the stress can be obtained based on the plastic constitution obtained from the experiments. It is shown that under the high-velocity crushing, the stress within the deformed zone decrease rapidly from the maximum lying at the impact end to the undeformed zone, and the higher the impact velocity is, the more nonuniformly the stress distributes. By measuring the average density of the deformed zone of the foam, the densification strain of the foams under dynamic crushing can be determined. Then combining the foam's stress-strain curve under the low-velocity compression, the dynamic plateau stress of the foams can be predicted. It is shown that both the densification strain and the foams' dynamic plateau stress predicted by employing the digital image process technology are in good agreement with the numerical simulations. The results show that both the plateau stress and the densification strain of the foams increase with the impact velocity, which is essentially caused by the localization of the foam's deformation under dynamic crushing.

1 INTRODUCTION

Metallic based cellular materials, such as honeycombs, foams and hollow spheres, have been developed and are growing in use as new engineering structural materials due to the notable advantages, such as the high relative stiffness and strength, the effective energy absorption, and so on. Research interests are mainly focused on the dynamic plateau stress of the cellular material, since it dictates the energy absorption capacity. Based on lots of numerical results, Ruan et. al [1] obtained an empirical expression of the plateau stress of hexagonal honeycombs under impact in terms of the impact velocity and the cell wall size. The analytical work were conducted in predicting the average dynamic plateau stress of the honeycombs from the structural point-of-view [2, 3], and the effects of the cells' geometry on the crushing strength of honeycombs were studied [4]. By using an idealized "R-P-P-L" model of the cellular materials, Tan et al [5] deduced the expression of the plateau stress of

cellular material under dynamic crushing, in which the densification strain of the cellular material is one of the key parameters.

The densification strain of the cellular material is usually estimated according to the stress-strain curve under quasi-static compression [5]. However, there is no persuading criterion in determining the densification point, since the plateau stress in the quasi-static stress-strain curve usually does not remain constant, especially for the foams. Besides, numerical results show that the densification strain depends on the crushing velocity [6]. The densification strain is deduced to be $(1 - 1.33\rho^* / \rho_s)$ for the hexagonal honeycombs under high-velocity crushing [2], where ρ^* and ρ_s are the density of the honeycomb and its base material.

The deformation of materials and structures can be detected and measured by using the digital image processing technology. Previously, this technology was successfully applied to distinguish and quantitatively evaluate the inhomogeneous deformation within the circular honeycombs under biaxial compression [7].

In the present paper, the digital image processing technology will be employed to predict both the densification strain and the plateau stress of the aluminium foam under dynamic crushing according to the variation of the density distribution within the foam during crushing and the quasi-static stress-strain curve. The results are compared to the numerical ones.

2 NUMERICAL SIMULATION

The numerical model of the foam with irregular cells is produced by a Voronoi program with the irregular factor being 0.5. The in-plane size of the foam model is 60mm*60mm and the out-of-plane size is 0.5mm. The finite element simulations are conducted using ANSYS/LS-DYNA. The foam specimen is placed on a fixed rigid base at one end, and crushed by a rigid plate (crushing plate) with a constant velocity at the other end, as shown in Fig.1.

Four levels of impact velocity are adopted: $V=1\text{m/s}$, 60m/s, 85m/s and 110m/s. The case of 1m/s is used to simulate the quasi-static loading. Shell elements are employed to mesh the cell walls with the thickness of the shell being 0.16mm, which produces the relative density of the foam as 0.1. An elastic, perfectly plastic model with $E=68\text{GPa}$ and $\sigma_{ys}=130\text{MPa}$ is adopted for the cell-wall material, where E and σ_{ys} are the Young's modulus and the yield stress, respectively.

The out-of-plane displacement of the nodes is constrained so as to prevent the specimen from out-of-plane bulking. A single surface contact AG (automatic general contact) is defined on the foam model, and ASTS (automatic surface-to-surface contact) is applied between the specimen and the two rigid plates, respectively. For both kinds of contact, the contact friction is not considered and the penalty factor is set to be 0.2.

Fig. 1 The finite element model

The deformed foam under compression is shown in Fig. 2, indication that with high impact velocity, most deformation of the foam is concentrated within a zone near the impact end, while the remained portion of the foam is almost undeformed. In contrast, in the low-velocity case with $V=1\text{m/s}$, as shown in Fig. 2(a), the deformation is more homogeneous within the whole specimen.

Fig. 2 The deformed foam with the global strain $\epsilon=0.5$

Fig. 3 Strain-stress curve of the foam

The stress-strain curves of the foams under impact with four levels of crushing velocity are plotted in Fig.3. It is shown that there are an obvious plateau stage in the curves for high-velocity cases, in

which the stress undulates around a certain level, as shown in Fig.3 (b)~(d); while the stress increases gradually with the strain during the compression after a short elastic stage in the low-velocity case ($V=1\text{m/s}$), as shown in Fig.3 (a).

3 DISTRIBUTION OF THE DENSITY WITHIN THE FOAM

To further investigate the inhomogeneous deformation of the foam under dynamic crushing, the distribution of the density within the deformed foam is calculated by employing the digital image processing technology. The simulation-generated pictures of the foam are divided into pieces with 18 pixels for the height of each piece, as shown in Fig. 4. Then by calculating the pixel ratio of the cell walls in each piece of the image, the distribution of the relative density within the foam can be obtained, as shown by the curve in the lower part of Fig. 4. In Fig. 4, the horizontal axis of the curve denotes the location of the piece relative to the initial height of the foam. Each step in the curve is corresponding to a piece of the foam, while the vertical scale denotes the relative density of the piece.

Fig. 4 Division of the image and the relative density for the pieces ($V=110\text{m/s}$, $\epsilon=0.3$)

Fig. 5 Evolutionment of density distribution within the foam ($V=110\text{m/s}$)

Fig. 6 Density distribution within the foam under impact with various crushing velocities

The evolvement of the density distribution of the foam with the global strain is exhibited in Fig. 5, in which the values above each curve denote the corresponding global strain ε . The relative density with the global strain $\varepsilon=0$ oscillates between 0.115 and 0.085, indicating the deviation of the density distribution within the undeformed foam is ± 0.015 . It is shown in Fig. 5 that the maximal density in the foam increases with the global strain until the global strain exceeds 0.4, and then the maximal density in the foam will remain almost as constant.

It is clear from Fig. 5 that the density of the foam decreases rapidly from the maximum lying at the impact end until the relative density reaches to about 0.2, and then it decends gently to the undeformed zone. Within the undeformed zone, the relative density of the foam oscillates around 0.1, which is the initial relative density of the foam. Thus, the foam is divided into a densified zone and an undensified zone by the critical relative density of 0.2, as shown with the red lines in Fig 5. The part with the relative density larger than 0.2 is regarded as the densified zone, while the remained part is named as the undensified zone. The boundary between the two zones is also marked in Figs. 2(b)-(d), showing they are all in reasonable locations.

The density distribution of the foams crushed under the three levels of velocity is compared with the global strain $\varepsilon=0.4$ and $\varepsilon=0.55$, respectively, as shown in Fig. 6. It is shown that with the increase of the crushing velocity, the maximal density located at the impact end is enhanced, and the densified zone is shrunk, meaning that a higher crushing velocity will result in more serious localization of the deformation with the same global strain.

4 DENSIFICATION STRAIN

It is observed in the numerical results that the lateral expansion of the foam during compressed is negligible. Thus by ignoring the lateral expansion of the foam, the relationship between the strain and the density of the foam is:

$$\varepsilon = 1 - \frac{\rho_{r0}}{\rho_{rc}} \quad (1)$$

where ρ_{r0} and ρ_{rc} are the initial and the current relative density of the foam, respectively.

Accordingly, the average strain in the densified zone of the foam can be obtained based on the distribution of the density within the zone, as listed in Table 1. It is shown that the strain in the densified zone increases with the crushing velocity, and is almost independent of the global strain.

Global Strain	0.25	0.30	0.35	0.40	0.45	0.50	0.55	0.60	0.65	0.70	0.75
v=60 m/s	0.70	0.72	0.72	0.74	0.73	0.75	0.74	0.73	0.72	0.74	0.73
v=85 m/s	0.79	0.80	0.78	0.80	0.82	0.79	0.78	0.80	0.80	0.79	0.80
v=110 m/s	0.79	0.81	0.83	0.85	0.82	0.83	0.81	0.83	0.84	0.85	0.85

Table 1 Average strain in the densified zone

Crushing velocity (m/s)	ε_d	σ_d [MPa]
60	0.729	1.566
85	0.796	2.431
110	0.828	3.419

Table 2 Predication on the densification strain and the plateau stress of the foams

By averaging the strain in the densified zone during compression, the densification strain of the foam, ε_d , can be obtained for each case, as listed in Table 2 and marked with the triangle points on the stress-strain curves in Figs. 3(b)-(d). It is shown that the obtained densification strain is almost located at the end of the plateau stage of the stress-strain curves, which justifies the validity of this method.

5 PLATEAU STRESS

According to the densification strains, ε_d , the corresponding stress, σ_d , can be found on the 1m/s strain-stress curve (Fig. 3(a)), as listed in Table 2. It was found in our previous experiments that the stress of the foams can be determined by the foams' current density [8]. Thus σ_d means the average stress level at the densified zone, since ε_d is calculated by the average density in this zone. Here σ_d is regarded as the plateau stress of the foam, and is plotted in Fig. 3 for verification, as shown as the horizontal line in Figs. 3(b)-(d). It is seen that σ_d provides a good prediction on the plateau stress of the foam under dynamic crushing.

It is clear from Table 2 that both the densification strain and the plateau stress of the foam increase with the impact velocity, which echoes the phenomenon that more serious localization of the deformation will be created under impact with higher-velocity. Evidently, the dynamic enhancement of the plateau stress is essentially caused by the serious localization of the deformation under the dynamic loading.

6 SUMMARY

The digital image processing technology is employed to analyze the mechanical behaviors of the aluminium foam under dynamic crushing. The following conclusions are drawn:

The deformation of the foam is concentrated within a zone near the impact end and accordingly the deformed foam under the dynamic crushing can be divided into a densified zone and an undensified zone. In the densified zone, the density of the foam decreases rapidly from the impact end to the densified/undensified boundary. The maximal density of the foam lies at the impact end and increases with the global strain until the global strain exceeds 0.4, and then the maximal density in the foam will remain almost as constant.

The average strain in the densified zone is independent of the global strain and increases with the impact velocity, which can well predict the densification strain of the foam under dynamic crushing. The corresponding stress in the 1m/s curve to the average strain in the densified zone can give a good prediction on the dynamic plateau stress of the foam. It is shown that the plateau stress of the foam increases with the crushing velocity, which is essentially caused by the serious localization of the deformation under the dynamic impact.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. Ruan, G. Lu, B. Wang, and T.X. Yu, In-plane dynamic crushing of honeycombs—a finite element study. *Int. J. Impact Eng.* 28.2 (2003) 161-182.
- [2] L.L. Hu, T.X. Yu, Dynamic crushing strength of hexagonal honeycombs, *Int. J. Impact Eng.* 37.5 (2010) 467-474.
- [3] L.L. Hu, T.X. Yu, Mechanical behavior of hexagonal honeycombs under low-velocity impact—theory and simulations, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* 50.20 (2013) 3152-3165.
- [4] L.L. Hu, F.F. You, T.X. Yu, Crushing strength of honeycombs with various cell wall angles, *Mater. Res. Innovations.* 15.s1 (2011) s155-s157.
- [5] P.J. Tan, S.R. Reid, J. J. Harrigan, Z. Zou, and S. Li, Dynamic compressive strength properties of aluminium foams. Part II—‘shock’ theory and comparison with experimental data and numerical models, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids.* 53.10 (2005) 2206-2230.
- [6] Z. Zou, S.R. Reid, P.J. Tan, S. Li, and J. J. Harrigan, Dynamic crushing of honeycombs and features of shock fronts, *Int. J. Impact Eng.* 36.1 (2009) 165-176.

- [7] L.L. Hu, T.X. Yu, Z.Y. Gao, and X.Q. Huang, The inhomogeneous deformation of polycarbonate circular honeycombs under in-plane compression, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* 50.7 (2008) 1224-1236.
- [8] L.L. Hu, X.Q. Huang, L.Q. Tang, and Y.P. Liu, Study on the Plastic Constitution and the Energy-Absorbing Characteristics of Aluminum Foam, *Key Eng. Mater.* 274 (2004) 235-240.